

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' INTELLECTUAL THINKING THROUGH TEACHING PHILOSOPHICAL DISCIPLINES

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Abstract: The article analyzes the importance of philosophical disciplines in the system of higher education and their role in the development of students' intelligence. It is emphasized that philosophy, being the basis of humanitarian knowledge contributes to the formation of critical and analytical thinking, the development of the ability to logical argumentation and independent judgment. The theoretical and methodological basis of the study is considered, including the concepts of L.S. Vygotsky on the socio-cultural nature of intelligence, the ideas of J. Piaget on the stages of cognitive development as well as the views of K. Jaspers and M. Heidegger on philosophy as a practice of “studying thinking” and posing the ultimate questions of human existence. Particular attention is paid to the pedagogical conditions of teaching philosophical disciplines which allow for the most effective disclosure of their potential in the intellectual development of students: problem-oriented learning, interactive discussions, work with philosophical primary sources, the use of multimedia and digital technologies. It is noted that philosophy performs an interdisciplinary function, combining humanitarian, natural scientific and social knowledge, thereby developing flexibility of thinking, the ability to reflect and perform interdisciplinary analysis. The article substantiates the thesis that teaching philosophical disciplines is not only an important component of the educational process, but also one of the key factors in the formation of the intellectual maturity of the individual. It is concluded that philosophy in the higher education system should be considered not as an auxiliary course, but as a strategic tool for the formation of critical, creative and socially responsible intelligence which is in demand in the conditions of modern society and global challenges.

Keywords: intelligence, philosophical disciplines, students, critical thinking, humanitarian knowledge, worldview.

1. INTRODUCTION

The modern system of higher education is going through a stage of transformation associated with the requirements of the information society, globalization processes and the accelerated development of science and technology. In such conditions, universities are faced with the task of not only imparting professional knowledge and skills to students, but also of developing intellectually mature individuals capable of critical thinking, independent analysis and responsible decision-making. One of the most important means of achieving this goal is the teaching of philosophical disciplines.

Philosophy is traditionally considered the core of humanitarian knowledge, fulfilling the function of the methodological basis of science and culture. It is not limited to the transmission of historical and philosophical information, but is focused on developing the ability to think systematically, identify contradictions and build reasoned conclusions. According to the fair assertion of K. Jaspers, philosophy is the “study of thinking” (Jaspers, 1954) and therefore its significance in the educational process goes far beyond the disciplinary framework. The intellectual development of students through philosophy is manifested in several key aspects: the formation of critical and dialectical thinking skills; the development of skills in logical analysis, argumentation and proof; the mastery of worldview categories and reflection on

fundamental questions of human existence; fostering interdisciplinary flexibility of thinking that allows for the integration of knowledge from different fields.

Vygotsky (1982) noted that the development of intelligence is associated with the internalization of cultural forms among which philosophy occupies one of the leading places due to its ability to form abstract and theoretical thinking. Similarly, J. Piaget (1972) emphasized the stage-by-stage nature of cognitive development that directly correlates with the acquisition of philosophical categories and logical structures.

Thus, the relevance of the study is due to the need to substantiate the role of philosophical disciplines as a strategic resource for the intellectual development of students in the context of the modern education system. The purpose of the article is to analyze the pedagogical potential of philosophy and to show how its teaching contributes to the formation of intellectual maturity, critical thinking and ideological culture of students.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The problem of developing students' intelligence through teaching philosophical disciplines has a rich research tradition, covering both classical philosophy and modern pedagogical science. Even in antiquity, philosophy was considered the basis of intellectual education. Plato in the Republic pointed out the need for philosophical education to form a rationally thinking citizen capable of making wise decisions. Aristotle emphasized the importance of logic and dialectics as tools for intellectual development (Aristotle, 1984). In the medieval tradition, Thomas Aquinas combined the rational and spiritual dimensions of philosophy, which formed the harmonious intellectual and value development of the individual.

F. Bacon and R. Descartes laid the foundations of the rationalistic approach, in which philosophy was viewed as a method of critical thinking. Kant argued that philosophy is the "teaching of reason" and forms the ability for autonomous thinking (Kant, 1994). Hegel emphasized the role of dialectics as a method of developing thinking, which has direct significance for the formation of the intellectual culture of students (Hegel, 1977).

K. Jaspers viewed philosophy as "the study of thinking" (Jaspers, 1954), and M. Heidegger associated philosophical education with posing the ultimate questions of human existence, which contributes to the development of deep reflection (Heidegger, 1953). These ideas are relevant for understanding how philosophy shapes the critical and ideological intellect of the modern student.

A significant contribution to the study of intellectual development was made by L.S. Vygotsky, who considered intelligence as a socio-cultural phenomenon and emphasized the importance of language and cultural forms, among which philosophy occupies a special place (Vygotsky, 1982). A.N. Leontiev developed this concept, linking intellectual development with activity (Leontiev, 1977).

J. Piaget considered cognitive development as a step-by-step formation of logical structures of thinking, which directly correlates with the acquisition of philosophical categories (Piaget, 1972). In Western pedagogy, B. Bloom's taxonomy (Bloom, 1956) has had a significant influence, where the highest cognitive levels (analysis, synthesis, evaluation) correspond precisely to philosophical forms of cognition.

Modern science emphasizes the need to integrate philosophical knowledge into the educational process. Thus, studies (Nussbaum, 2010; Hadot, 2002) show that philosophy develops critical thinking skills, empathy, and the ability to engage in

dialogue in students, which are integral elements of intellectual maturity. Russian scientists (Ilyin, 2016; Stepin, 2009) note that philosophical education develops in students the ability for interdisciplinary thinking, which is necessary in the context of an increasingly complex society.

An analysis of philosophical and pedagogical literature allows us to conclude that teaching philosophical disciplines plays a unique role in the development of students' intellect. It not only promotes the acquisition of knowledge, but also develops the ability to reflect, criticize, create, and synthesize across disciplines. Thus, philosophy acts as a strategic instrument for the intellectual education of the individual.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the work is determined by the interdisciplinary nature of the problem under study, which combines philosophical, psychological, pedagogical and cultural approaches. Since the aim of the study is to identify the role of philosophical disciplines in the intellectual development of students, the methodology includes both general scientific and special methods of analysis.

Firstly, a philosophical and methodological approach was used, which involves considering intellectual development as a process of forming thinking in a broad cultural and historical context. Here, the support is provided by the ideas of L.S. Vygotsky on the socio-cultural nature of intelligence, J. Piaget's concepts on the stages of cognitive development, as well as the views of K. Jaspers and M. Heidegger on philosophy as a practice for the formation of reflexive and analytical thinking.

Secondly, a systematic approach is applied, which allows us to consider the intellectual development of a student's personality in the unity of cognitive, value and communicative components of forms of thinking. This approach provides a holistic understanding of how philosophical disciplines impact different levels of intelligence, from basic logical operations to complex ideological and critical forms of thinking.

Thirdly, the psychological and pedagogical methodological level is of great importance, which involves relying on the works of A.N. Leontiev, B.G. Ananyev and B. Bloom. Bloom's taxonomy of educational goals allows us to classify the intellectual results of teaching philosophy - from the reproduction of knowledge to analysis, synthesis and evaluation.

The work also uses a comparative-analytical method to compare various pedagogical practices of teaching philosophical disciplines, a hermeneutic method to analyze philosophical texts and their interpretation in the educational process, as well as a method of pedagogical modeling, which allows us to identify optimal conditions for the intellectual development of students using philosophical means.

Thus, the research methodology is comprehensive, combining philosophical analysis, pedagogical theory and psychological concepts of intelligence development. It provides scientific substantiation for conclusions about how teaching philosophical disciplines contributes to the development of students' intellectual maturity in the context of the modern higher education system.

Analysis and results of the study. Intellectual development has long been a subject of philosophical reflection, since it is philosophy that traditionally poses questions about the nature of reason, consciousness and knowledge. In ancient thought, we encounter the first systematic attempts to understand the intellectual development of man. Thus, Plato considered knowledge as a process of the soul's

recollection of eternal ideas, and associated intellectual development with the ascent from sensory perceptions to the world of true forms. Aristotle, on the contrary, emphasized the active role of experience, categorical thinking and logic, laying the foundations for understanding rational activity as a step towards comprehending the truth.

In medieval philosophy, intellectual development was considered in close connection with theological doctrines. Thomas Aquinas argued that human reason is a gift from God, and intellectual improvement serves as a means of approaching divine truth. The Renaissance brought a rethinking of human intelligence as an autonomous creative force. Humanist philosophers, in particular Pico dellaMirandola, asserted the idea of the limitless possibilities of reason and the ability of man to shape his own future.

In the New Age, the problem of intellectual development received a rationalistic and empirical understanding. R. Descartes and B. Spinoza saw reason as a universal instrument of knowledge, while F. Bacon and J. Locke emphasized the role of experience and education. Kant's critical philosophy made a significant contribution by substantiating the structural forms of knowledge and pointing out the limits of human reason.

In the 19th–20th centuries, philosophical thought shifted its emphasis to the socio-cultural factors of intellectual development. G. Hegel interpreted reason as the highest stage in the development of the Absolute Spirit, and K. Marx linked the formation of intelligence with work activity and social relations. In the phenomenology of E. Husserl and the existentialism of J.-P. Sartre, intellect is interpreted not only as a rational structure, but also as a personal-existential dimension of human existence.

Modern philosophical approaches to intellectual development combine ideas from classical philosophy with data from cognitive science and psychology. Within the framework of the post-non-classical paradigm, intelligence is understood as a multidimensional phenomenon that includes not only logical-rational operations, but also intuition, imagination, creativity and emotional intelligence. In the context of the information society, philosophy points to the need for critical thinking, digital literacy and the ability to integrate diverse sources of knowledge.

Thus, the theoretical foundations of intellectual development in the philosophical context testify to its versatility: from the metaphysical constructions of antiquity to the interdisciplinary syntheses of modernity. Philosophy not only defines the fundamental categories of reason and thinking, but also forms methodological guidelines that allow us to understand intellectual development as a dynamic, culturally determined and value-laden process.

Philosophical disciplines occupy a special place in the system of higher education, as they are aimed not only at the transfer of knowledge, but also at the formation of a holistic worldview, the development of critical thinking and intellectual independence of the individual. A student, mastering philosophy, not only becomes familiar with the history of ideas and teachings, but also learns to think more deeply, logically and systematically, which ultimately contributes to the formation of a mature intellect.

Above all, philosophy helps students master the art of asking questions. Unlike most disciplines, which focus on ready-made answers, philosophy courses develop the ability to doubt, to seek the basis for certain statements, to analyze even what seems obvious. This develops in students the ability to think independently, to go beyond the norm, which is a key element of intellectual development.

Secondly, philosophical disciplines contribute to the formation of a logical culture. Studying the laws and forms of thinking, the rules of argumentation and proof allows students not only to avoid logical errors, but also to build clear, consistent reasoning. Such skills are necessary not only in the academic environment, but also in future professional activities, where analytics, decision-making and the ability to justify one's own position are important.

Thirdly, philosophy enriches students with cultural and historical knowledge, forming their understanding of the evolution of human thought. Familiarity with the philosophical teachings of antiquity, the Middle Ages, the New Age and modern times allows us to see how ideas about the world, man and society have developed. This not only broadens one's horizons, but also develops the ability to evaluate contemporary problems in the context of the historical continuity of ideas.

Philosophical disciplines are of particular importance for the development of students' value consciousness. Understanding the issues of the meaning of life, freedom, responsibility, justice, and truth contributes to the formation of a mature personality capable of moral choice and responsible behavior. Thus, philosophy plays not only a cognitive but also an educational role, developing in students the ability to correlate their actions with universal human values.

It is worth mentioning the role of philosophical disciplines in the development of interdisciplinary thinking. Modern science is characterized by increasing specialization, which often leads to a "narrowness" of professional horizons. Philosophy helps students see the relationship between different areas of knowledge, to understand the integrity of the picture of the world, which is an important condition for the formation of universal intellectual competencies.

In addition, philosophy develops students' communicative skills. In the process of discussions, debates, and philosophical debates, students learn to respect other points of view, formulate their own arguments, and defend them correctly and logically. This creates a culture of dialogue and tolerance, which is especially important in the context of a globalizing world and the diversity of cultural traditions.

Thus, philosophical disciplines in the higher education system perform a multifaceted function: they develop analytical, logical, ideological, ethical and communication skills in students. All this together contributes not only to the growth of their intellectual potential, but also to the development of a harmonious, socially responsible personality, ready for active professional and social activities.

Effective teaching of philosophy in educational institutions is impossible without the creation of special pedagogical conditions that ensure a high level of knowledge acquisition, the development of critical thinking and the formation of personal value systems. Modern pedagogical science considers these conditions as a set of organizational, methodological, psychological and didactic factors that create a favorable environment for the acquisition of philosophical knowledge.

Firstly, the most important condition is the correct organization of the educational process. The teacher must use such forms and methods of work that maximally stimulate the cognitive activity of students. Practical classes in the format of discussions, debates, round tables, analysis of philosophical texts must be added to traditional lectures. This approach develops the skills of independent search for truth, teaches argumentation and respect for other points of view. In addition, a significant factor is the systematicity and consistency of the presentation of the material. Philosophy as a discipline requires strict logic, a clear structure and a step-by-step disclosure of the categorical apparatus. The sequence of presentation of

concepts allows students to master complex theoretical constructs without being overloaded and to form stable knowledge.

The second important condition is taking into account the individual characteristics of students. Philosophy is not only a theory, but also a practice of understanding one's own worldview. Therefore, in the teaching process, a personality-oriented approach should be used, which involves relying on the life experience of students, taking into account their interests, level of training and cultural background. The teacher must create an atmosphere of trust and dialogue, where each student can freely express his or her views. This avoids formalism and turns philosophy into living knowledge that is directly related to the student's personality.

The effectiveness of teaching is significantly increased when interactive teaching methods are used. For example: problem lectures, heuristic conversations, the case method, situational analysis. During such classes, students do not passively listen to the material, but become active participants in the cognitive process. The use of creative tasks – writing essays, philosophical diaries, conducting mini-research and projects is of a particular importance. Such work stimulates creativity and develops the ability to apply philosophical ideas to real life situations.

Modern pedagogical conditions are impossible without the introduction of digital technologies. Teaching philosophy requires access to electronic libraries, multimedia presentations, philosophical forums and online platforms for discussions. Visualization of information (graphs, diagrams, mind maps) facilitates the perception of abstract categories. In addition, modern students perceive material better in an interactive form, so the use of online tests, virtual seminars, video lectures and podcasts significantly expands didactic possibilities.

The formation of a stable motivation for studying philosophy plays a special role. For this, it is important for the teacher to show the practical significance of philosophical knowledge in the life of a modern person. Philosophy helps to understand the meaning of life, values, problems of freedom, justice and responsibility - that is, those questions that concern everyone. A teacher should not just convey information, but inspire students to philosophize, develop in them the ability to independently seek answers to existential questions. This is the true value of philosophical education.

Effective teaching of philosophy is possible only in a supportive educational environment. The student must feel that his opinion is respected, his ideas are valued, and mistakes are seen as steps to further development. This atmosphere helps to develop confidence in one's own intellectual abilities and encourages active participation in the educational process.

4. CONCLUSION

Thus, the pedagogical conditions for effective teaching of philosophy include a set of factors: organizational and methodological support, a personality-oriented approach, activation of cognitive activity, use of modern technologies, formation of motivation and creation of a psychologically comfortable environment. Their combination ensures a high level of assimilation of the material and turns philosophy into an important tool for shaping the worldview and critical thinking of students.

The pedagogical conditions for effective teaching of philosophy are a combination of didactic, methodological, organizational and psychological factors that ensure the formation of a holistic philosophical worldview, critical thinking and

the ability to independently analyze in students. In the course of the conducted research, several key provisions can be identified that are of fundamental importance for improving the quality of philosophical education.

Firstly, the most important condition is the creation of a developing educational environment that promotes students' intellectual activity. Philosophy as a discipline requires not mechanical memorization, but thoughtful analysis and interpretation of ideas. Therefore, the organization of the educational process should be based on dialogue, discussions, problem-based learning and research methods. The teacher, in this case, acts not only as a bearer of knowledge, but also as a moderator of the process, stimulating students to independently search for truth.

Secondly, it is very important to take into account the individual characteristics of students. Effective teaching of philosophy is impossible without taking into account the level of students' preparation, their personal interests, motivation and cognitive styles. The use of a differentiated approach, the use of interdisciplinary connections, and the integration of traditional and innovative teaching methods make philosophical education more accessible, flexible, and effective.

Thirdly, an important pedagogical condition is the integration of modern educational technologies. The use of multimedia resources, electronic libraries, virtual lectures and online discussions expands the possibilities of philosophical education, making it interactive and closer to the needs of modern youth. Incorporating digital tools into the teaching of philosophy allows students to engage more deeply with texts, critically examine different approaches, and relate philosophical ideas to real-world issues.

Fourthly, the importance of a value-oriented approach in teaching philosophy cannot be underestimated. Philosophy is not limited to theoretical knowledge; it forms students' worldviews, moral guidelines, and civic position. Therefore, the teacher must direct the learning process not only towards the transfer of knowledge, but also towards the development of a person capable of thinking freely, critically and responsibly.

Fifthly, effective teaching of philosophy requires continuous professional development of the teacher. A modern teacher must master both classical philosophical concepts and modern theories, be competent in the field of pedagogy, psychology and information technology. Continuous professional development and participation in scientific research allow the teacher to remain relevant and authoritative in the eyes of students.

Thus, it can be concluded that the pedagogical conditions for effective teaching of philosophy include: creation of a developing educational environment; consideration of individual characteristics of students; integration of modern technologies; value-oriented approach; professional development of the teacher.

These conditions together form the foundation for improving the quality of philosophical education, ensure the formation of a holistic worldview in students and contribute to the training of competent specialists capable of critical understanding and constructive solutions to the problems of modern society. As a result, philosophy fulfills its key function - it becomes not only an academic discipline, but also an important element in the formation of the spiritual culture of the individual and society.

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